

Personal Financial Planning Research : A TCCM Framework Analysis of Theories Contexts Characteristics and Methodologies

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Abstract

This study examines patterns, trends, and research gaps in personal financial planning using a with the TCCM (theories, context, characteristics, and methodology) framework. A dataset of 181 publications from the Scopus database (2000–2025) was analyzed. while the TCCM review provides deeper insights into theoretical foundations, contexts, and methodological approaches. The findings highlight strong associations between financial literacy, demographic and socio-economic factors, psychological parameters, and their influence on financial well-being. Although limited to English-language studies from a single database, this research offers valuable implications for policymakers, regulators, and academics by synthesizing diverse literature and clarifying antecedents, outcomes, mediators, and moderators in personal financial planning. To the best of our knowledge, TCCM review in the domain, offering a structured roadmap for future research.

Keywords

Financial Literacy, Financial Planning, TCCM Framework, Financial Management.

Introduction

The application of financial concepts to an individual's or family's financial decisions is known as personal finance. It deals with how individuals or families acquire, allocate, save, and utilize monetary resources over time, considering different financial risks and forthcoming life events (Sharma and Bohara,2010). Finance is a broad term that actually refers to the issues concerning money. Obviously, one important social-economic measure of well-being that people in all cultures look forward to is money. To meet future financial requirements and maintain a healthy financial condition, personal financial planning is crucial (Mahapatra et al.,2019).

Objective of study

1. This study will answer the following research questions (RQs).
2. RQ1What are the most significant theories, contexts, characteristics and methodologies in the field?
3. RQ2. What potential paths may personal financial planning research follow in the future?

Review of Literature

There are various aspects of financial planning including financial planning, tax planning, investment planning, retirement planning, estate planning, risk management, and cash flow management (Altfest,2004). Over time, due to the constant growth and complexity of financial issues, society has faced a higher cost of living and diverse financial problems (Baker et al., 2023). Financial literacy enables individual to make wise financing decision, an essential ability for managing life events and household budgeting (Garg and Singh, 2018). Good understanding of finance focuses further information on individual financial planning to anticipate the negative impacts that poor financial planning can have on their lives and vice versa. Personal financial planning cannot be the same forever, it requires timely review depending on a person's transition from one life stage to another, and changes also depend on the ever-changing economic and financial environment. Each stage of life requires distinct financial strategies because financial priorities change with age. Many studies have been performed on systematic literature review related to personal financial planning such as antecedents and consequences of personal financial management behaviour (Goyal et al., 2021); exploring two decades of personal financial planning (Pande et al., 2024); dynamics of personal financial management (Shi et al., 2024).

The whole document has been structured into distinct sections and subsections. Sections in a review article may be categorized as 1. Introduction, 2. Methodology, 3. The article covers the TCCM analysis. 4. Ultimately, the discussion of the implications and suggested frameworks, alongside a conclusion and directions for future research, has been compiled in the subsequent sections of the document (Paul and Menzies, 2023).

Methodology

A substantial quantity of published research is analyzed through TCCM (theories, context, characteristics, and methodology approach), which was developed by Paul and Serrano in 2019. Additionally, since 2018, the use of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) criteria in review publications has been

on the rise (Sharma and Laishram, 2024). The PRISMA framework shows a clear and thorough method that involves gathering data, assessing it, and using systematic ways to find, select, review, and study important literature.

This study will answer the following research questions (RQs).

RQ1 What are the most significant theories, contexts, characteristics and methodologies in the field?

RQ2. What potential paths may personal financial planning research follow in the future?

Data extraction, inclusion and exclusion criteria

The methodology involves defining criteria for inclusion and exclusion, eliminate duplicate information, conducting an extensive bibliometric analysis, and performing an insightful content analysis. This organized approach enhances the validity and reliability of the research findings. The way we gather data using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) method is illustrated in Figure 1 (Moher et al., 2009). **Figure 1.** PRISMA framework outlining the literature search procedure

The final query string was:

The diagrammatic presentation of the data extraction is shown below using PRISMA

“(“personal finance planning” OR “personal financial practices” OR “household finance” OR “money management” OR “family finance planning” OR “personal financial behavior” OR “personal financial management” AND “financial literacy” AND “retirement planning” AND “saving” AND “investment” AND “risk management” AND “budgetary planning” AND “insurance” AND “estate planning”))”

Findings

3.1 Main information

In the years from 2000 to 2025, 181 relevant journal publications obtained from Scopus addressed various aspects of personal financial planning. This section thoroughly looks at the important findings from the bibliometric analysis. A comprehensive overview of 181 documents chosen for examination published in 116 journals is displayed in Figure 2. It was observed that every article possesses a citation score of 15.69% per document (average score) and, on average, 3 authors worked together in this specific research domain. The quantity of articles within this theme experienced an annual growth rate in article production of 2.81% suggesting that there is considerable research opportunity in this area. The presence of 437 authors in this dataset suggests that the field of study holds considerable interest for a large group of researchers and represents.

Source (s): Biblioshiny using RStudio

Figure 2: Showing main information for the final data 181 documents

3.2 Publication trend

In the years that followed, the release of academic papers regarding personal financial planning significant rise, reaching a high point in 2025, with an impressive more than twenty articles. The gradual rise in academic papers on personal financial planning from 2014 to 2025 can be ascribed to various factors. Most of current study collaboration with behavioural finance in context of personal financial management.

Source (s): Biblioshiny using RStudio
Figure 3: Showing the publication trend of articles

3.3 TCCM analysis

To address RQ1, we build upon the TCCM (theories, context, characteristics, and methodology) framework (Paul and Rosado-Serrano, 2019). We organized this evaluation according to the TCCM framework, which lists the most widely used theories (T), contexts (C), characteristics (C), and methodology (M) in a field. The TCCM framework explains the theoretical and empirical aspects of a study issue, so overcoming the limitations of traditional systematic reviews. TCCM Analysis offers guidance for future research and fills in the gaps found by previous studies (Paul and Rosado-Serrano, 2019; Pandey et al., 2024).

3.3.1 Applied Theory (T)

This study has examined the important ideas currently being addressed in the personal financial planning literature, which is crucial for the future development of the discipline. theory, technological acceptance model, capital asset pricing model (CAPM), efficient market hypothesis (EMH), theory of reasoned action, social cognitive theory, behavioural finance theory and prospect theory, Maslow's need hierarchy theory, theory of mental accounting, and family resource management model. Incorporating a personal financial planning or future orientation framework offers the relevant research field new perspectives to consider.

Several theoretical frameworks contribute significantly to understanding personal financial planning. Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) emphasizes rational decision-making by balancing risk and return, providing a foundation for portfolio diversification and risk tolerance assessment. The Transtheoretical Model of Behavior Change (TTM) explains how individuals move through stages—precontemplation to maintenance—when adopting saving habits, linking the desire to save with actual saving behavior. The Behavioral Life-Cycle Hypothesis (BLCH) highlights mental accounting, where individuals categorize income, assets, and future earnings, shaping saving and spending patterns through mental

budgeting. Similarly, the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) stresses the role of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control in influencing financial intentions and behavior, often with financial literacy as a mediating factor. Family Financial Socialization Theory underscores the intergenerational transfer of financial knowledge, attitudes, and practices within households, shaping lifelong financial behavior. Prospect Theory adds a behavioral lens by showing how individuals weigh losses more heavily than gains, affecting saving and investment decisions. The Financial Capability Model integrates budgeting, numeracy, and decision-making capacity as essential components of sound financial planning. Moreover, Self-Determination Theory (SDT) explains how varying levels of motivation—amotivation, controlled, and autonomous—affect financial literacy and overall well-being. Finally, Goal Setting Theory provides a systematic framework for articulating and pursuing financial goals, thereby enhancing long-term planning outcomes. Together, these theories offer comprehensive insights into the psychological, behavioral, and social dimensions of personal financial planning

3.3.2 Applied Context (C)

As per Paul et al. (2017) Context pertains to the conditions or environment in which a specific study was carried out. To investigate the boundaries of any research field, the key is in recognizing its geographical origin (Khalek & Chakraborty,2023). Contexts (C) in the TCCM also indicates the research geography area of focus. By taking into account different geographic contexts, researchers can better understand the particulars of attitudes, perceptions, and actions related to personal financial planning. The current study focuses on the nations and particular group that have conducted research on personal financial planning. With the systematic review, it has been noted that most of study were conduct in USA, Malaysia, India and south Africa (Boon et al., 2011; Kock et al., 2012; Lai and Tan, 2009) ; Gen -Y , Public sector, undergraduate students, student in Malasia (Masran and Hassan,2017; Mokhtar et al., 2015; Wahab ,2024; Azer & Mohamad, 2018); Working professional and Working adult , Household, women and working women, school faculties, Generation X and Generation Y, Legal Practitioners; rural investor , Teacher in higher education in India (Singh et al., 2018; Godase et al., 2024; Mahapatra et al ., 2022 ; Kumar et al ., 2019; Gautama, 2022; Lone and Bhatt ,2024; Shobha et al.,2020; Umesh et al.,2024); Consumer centric, MBA students, Young Adult ,Women in the USA (Guzman and Paswan,2019; Murphy and Yetmar,2010; Lusardi and Mitchell, 2011) ; Female worker in Indonesia (Larisa et al., 2021) ; Widows in USA (Korb,2010) ;Women and Gen -Y in south Africa (Venter and Kruger , 2017 ; Deventer ,2020); lower-middle class and public servant in Brazil (Miotto and Parente, 2015 ; Vieira et al.,2023); Collage student (Kidwell and Turris, 2004) ; University student in turkey (Altintas ,2011); Individual and Household in Netherland (Brounen et al.,2016); Gen-Y in Bangkok (Srisorn and Chayanon, 2023); College Graduates in China (Huang ,2016) These findings indicate that there is a necessity to explore additional field for upcoming research studies. Likewise, the highest quantity of studies has been carried out by developed nations with a smaller proportion of research conducted by developing nations. But emerging economy like India and Malaysia give huge contribution in this field. In other words, a future gap exists in collaborating with developing countries on the empirical basis of the subject area.

3.3.3 Applied Characteristics (C)

Personal financial planning has become a very significant procedure for an individual over the past few decades. Understanding the various elements that speed up personal financial planning is therefore crucial. A comprehensive review of the literature revealed that a wide range of factors impact financial behavior. These factors include, among other things, socioeconomic and demographic characteristics, psychological and personality characteristics, social characteristics, financial literacy, expert financial advice, environmental factors, technological factors, situational factors, cultural influences, and financial experience (Goyal et al., 2021).

3.3.4 Applied Methodology (M)

This section can be utilized by researcher aiming to enhance the techniques applied in previous research and examine creative methods to have greater insight of the phenomenon personal financial planning. Research flow in the field is significantly driven by empirical studies, and apparently, quantitative research design constitutes a substantial portion of this empirical literature. (Mamo et al, 2024; Barbic et al., 2019; Gautam et al., 2022; Wahab et al, 2024; Kock et al., 2012) Survey, random sampling and Convenience sampling most preferred technique used for data collection (Fisher and Montalto, 2010; Lone and Bhat, 2022; Singh et al., 2018) It necessitates additional research utilizing longitudinal data and cross-sectional study to obtain a deeper understanding of individual perceptions regarding their personal financial planning (Venter and Kruger, 2017; Gutter et al., 2012; Ghaffar et al., 2022; Godase et al., 2023). Researchers in the field have utilized different methods to analyse the data, primarily employing several forms of regression (Hierarchical regression, Sobel regression, Probit and Logit regression) and other analysis tools succeeded through partial least squares structural equation modeling, structural equation modeling, exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses using AMOS other same study use KMO and Bartlett's test, MANOVA, ANOVA, chi-square, t-test, Tukey test as well as content and thematic analysis. (Larisa et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2018; Lai, 2019; Boon et al., 2011; Mahapatra et al., 2022; Van Deventer, 2020; Kidwell and Turrisi 2004) In future research, studies might choose qualitative and mixed-method research designs. In terms of data collection methods, case studies or qualitative interviews could result in unique findings.

4 Future Research Avenues

To address RQ2, we revealed substantial gaps and recommend new directions for upcoming research. Personal financial planning essential for ensuring a resilient future, especially in the field of retirement and insurance planning. Undoubtedly, previous literature has had a significant impact on the establishment of personal financial planning research, from its conceptual foundation to the creation of its measurement tools. Although recent studies on personal financial planning have resulted in significant contributions in later years, the integration of the literature has revealed substantial gaps in comprehending the topic. These gaps create opportunities for future theoretical advancement and research on personal financial planning. Personal finance research still faces several conceptual, theoretical, and methodological gaps that require attention. At the conceptual level, future studies should identify the core financial concepts every consumer must understand and evaluate whether current frameworks effectively help individuals achieve financial goals. There is also a need to explore other overlooked elements that shape personal financial planning. From a theoretical perspective, applying behavioral science to encourage positive financial behavior and understanding whether saving is perceived as favorable across different life stages remain important questions. Regarding the antecedents of personal financial planning, researchers should investigate the role of financial training programs, personal preference variables (such as self-control, materialism, and impulsivity), and the influence of economic disturbances or crises (e.g., the COVID-19 pandemic) on financial risk management and socialization processes. Similarly, the role of moderators—such as financial education, personality traits, cognitive perceptions, and emotional states—needs further examination, as does the impact of mediators like locus of control and personality in shaping financial behavior. In terms of outcomes, the links between financial well-being, financial capabilities, decision-making, and quality of life require deeper analysis, especially concerning how debt and societal resources affect

long-term well-being. Additionally, measurement issues call for the development of valid and reliable scales to assess investment planning, technology readiness, and family financial socialization. Finally, methodological gaps highlight the need for stratified or quota sampling to avoid biases, the use of longitudinal and event history analyses to capture life-stage changes, and qualitative approaches such as interviews and focus groups to enrich understanding of financial attitudes and behaviors.

Conclusion

Personal financial management is a developing but increasingly important area that significantly impacts individuals' lives. This study aimed to offer an in-depth primer on personal finance planning by examining the existing literature through a mixed method that incorporates the TCCM framework. The study systematically examined trends, influential contributors, and key thematic clusters within the literature. The findings underscore the increasing scholarly interest in personal finance since the mid-2010s, particularly in areas such as financial literacy, behavioral finance, and financial socialization. Additionally, the TCCM analysis showed that theories such as the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Life Cycle Hypothesis are widely adopted to explore personal financial behavior and its outcomes. The study also points out new topics and areas that need more research, especially how technology is not well included in personal financial planning studies and how some important factors that influence financial behavior are not fully examined. These findings set the stage for future research to explore more thoroughly the effects of digital tools, financial technology, and changing consumer behavior. Overall, this research contributes valuable knowledge to the academic community and provides a foundation for developing more effective, theory-driven, and practical financial education and planning strategies.

Limitation of the Study

The current study contributes in several ways to the body of knowledge already available on the variables affecting financial well-being. The study's conclusions indicate that several factors affect both short-term and long-term personal financial planning. The findings could be used to develop financial education programs that will help business school instructors impart the information and abilities needed to manage their money in terms of retirement planning and savings, improving their overall financial well-being. Through literature review finds that socialization significantly influence to financial decision. This work emphasizes how crucial it is for financial advisors to thoroughly explain difficult financial ideas in manners that their clients can easily grasp. Through a consistent program of open workshops and seminars, financial planners might begin to address this demand for financial literacy instruction. Such research can be significant for young working professionals who encounter a dilemma while engaging in personal financial planning while making financial choices. Thus, we thoroughly described the conceptual and empirical landscape of personal financial planning by carefully reviewing the literature and using the hybrid the approach. It would give researchers the information they need to advance the research agenda and assist them in understanding the present state of research in this domain today. The recognition of potential research paths from each thematic cluster and the TCCM framework is another advantage of the present study. Adhering closely to these considerations will assist in eliminating the current ambiguity in the field and facilitate more thorough future research.

Although the research employed a systematic literature review using a hybrid framework, its results are not without constraints. Since we limited our investigation to the SCOPUS database repository, other significant databases such as Web of Science, EBSCO, and JSTOR could be considered by researchers in the future. The results of our research depend on the information obtained through our search string, which presents a risk of missing some important studies. Additionally, because of the authors deficiencies in expertise in languages apart from English, studies from various languages are still available for review. Considering the objective of our study, we limited ourselves to a general overview of personal financial planning. Nevertheless, for the advancement of research in this area, we recommend that future researchers conduct a thorough investigation of each component of personal financial planning.

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